

Decoding CUDA Binary - Special Registers

Here we list all special registers we have observed. The first column is the encoded value. The second column contains the name of the special register, which nearly always begins with the text "SR_". In cases where different architectures disagree regarding the name associated with an encoding, we list the older name in the third column.

Not all special registers are available on every GPU architecture. Additionally, the names produced by the disassembler will vary in formatting depending on its version. In particular, capitalization of the letters may differ, and dots may be replaced by underscores.

Encoding	Special Register	Alternate SR
0	SR_LANEID	
1	SR_CLOCK	
2	SR_VIRTCFG	
3	SR_VIRTID	
4	SR_PM0	
5	SR_PM1	
6	SR_PM2	
7	SR_PM3	
8	SR_PM4	
9	SR_PM5	
10	SR_PM6	
11	SR_PM7	
16	SR_PRIM_TYPE	
17	SR_INVOCATION_ID	
18	SR_Y_DIRECTION	
19	SR_THREAD_KILL	
20	SM_SHADER_TYPE	
21	SR_DIRECTCBEWRITEADDRESSLOW	
22	SR_DIRECTCBEWRITEADDRESSHIGH	
23	SR_DIRECTCBEWRITEENABLED	
24	SR_MACHINE_ID_0	
25	SR_MACHINE_ID_1	
26	SR_MACHINE_ID_2	
27	SR_MACHINE_ID_3	
28	SR_AFFINITY	
29	SR_INVOCATION_INFO	
30	SR_WSCALEFACTOR_XY	
31	SR_WSCALEFACTOR_Z	
32	SR_TID	
33	SR_TID.X	
34	SR_TID.Y	
35	SR_TID.Z	
36	SR_CTA_PARAM	
37	SR_CTAID.X	
38	SR_CTAID.Y	
39	SR_CTAID.Z	
40	SR_NTID	
41	SR_CIRQUEUEINCRMINUSONE	SR_NTID.X
42	SR_NLATC	SR_NTID.Y
43	SR_NTID.Z	
44	SR_GRIDPARAM	
45	SR_NCTAID.X	
46	SR_NCTAID.Y	
47	SR_NCTAID.Z	
48	SR_SWINLO	

49	SR_SWINSZ
50	SR_SMEMSZ
51	SR_SMEMBANKS
52	SR_LWINLO
53	SR_LWINSZ
54	SR_LMEMLOSZ
55	SR_LMEMHIOFF
56	SR_EQMASK
57	SR_LTMASK
58	SR_LEMASK
59	SR_GTMASK
60	SR_GEMASK
61	SR_REGALLOC
62	SR_CTXADDR
64	SR_GLOBALERRORSTATUS
66	SR_WARPERRORSTATUS
67	SR_WARPERRORSTATUSCLEAR
72	SR_PM_HI0
73	SR_PM_HI1
74	SR_PM_HI2
75	SR_PM_HI3
76	SR_PM_HI4
77	SR_PM_HI5
78	SR_PM_HI6
79	SR_PM_HI7
80	SR_CLOCKLO
81	SR_CLOCKHI
82	SR_GLOBALTIMERLO
83	SR_GLOBALTIMERHI
96	SR_HWTASKID
97	SR_CIRCULARQUEUEENTRYINDEX
98	SR_CIRCULARQUEUEENTRYADDRESSLOW
99	SR_CIRCULARQUEUEENTRYADDRESSHIGH